

Nature of Addition Compounds of Naphthoxides of Titanium(IV) with Some Amides and Phosphoryl Ligands

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Di- and tri-chlorotitanium(IV)naphthoxides form compounds of composition $TiCl_2(OC_{10}H_7)_2 \cdot 2L$ and $TiCl_3(OC_{10}H_7) \cdot 2L$, while titanium tetranaphthoxide naphtholate forms compounds of composition $Ti(OC_{10}H_7)_4 \cdot L$, where L stands for phosphoryl and amide ligands. Based upon elemental analysis, conductance, molecular weight, T. G. A. and infrared spectral studies, their structures have been elucidated.

COMPARED to alkoxides¹ and phenoxides^{2,3} little attention has been focussed on the chemistry of metal naphthoxides though they find applications as homogeneous catalysts in synthetic organic reactions^{4,5}. In our earlier communication⁶, we have reported the synthesis of naphthoxides of titanium(IV) and elucidated their structures. In continuation of these investigations, we now report the addition compounds of naphthoxides of titanium(IV) with some amides and phosphoryl ligands to establish their Lewis acid character.

Experimental

Titanium naphthoxides, $Ti(OC_{10}H_7)_4 \cdot C_{10}H_7OH$, $TiCl_3(OC_{10}H_7)$ and $TiCl_2(OC_{10}H_7)_2$ were prepared by the methods reported earlier⁶. All the chemicals used were AR grade and were purified by standard methods. Addition compounds of naphthoxides of titanium(IV) with various amides and phosphoryl ligands were prepared by reacting benzene solution or suspension of a known weight of parent titanium naphthoxide with the ligands under controlled experimental conditions because reactions were exothermic. The content were stirred for about 6 h, when the components went into solution and the compounds were isolated by the addition of petroleum ether. In some of the cases, the components were refluxed and the crystalline compounds separated out on cooling the resulting solutions. These were then filtered and dried under vacua.

Titanium was estimated as titanium dioxide and chlorine by Volhard's method. Molecular weights of the adducts were determined cryoscopically in nitrobenzene. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded using Perkin-Elmer 337 and 621 spectrophotometer. Thermal studies of the compounds were carried out on a Stanton Model AD-2 thermogravimetric balance.

Results and Discussion

Di- and tri-chlorotitanium(IV)naphthoxides form compounds of composition $TiCl_2(OC_{10}H_7)_2 \cdot 2L$

and $TiCl_3(OC_{10}H_7) \cdot 2L$ with *N*-methylformamide, *N,N'*-dimethylformamide, *N*-methylacetamide, *N,N'*-dimethylacetamide, dimethylsulphoxide, hexamethylformamide and triphenylphosphine oxide, while titanium tetranaphthoxide naphtholate forms compounds of composition $Ti(OC_{10}H_7)_4 \cdot L$ with these ligands. Stoichiometric composition of these compounds has been established by elemental analysis (Table 1). The compounds are moisture sensitive but stable in dry atmosphere. Molar conductances using millimolar solutions of most of these compounds in nitrobenzene are very low compared to the values of 1 : 1 electrolytes, thus indicating their predominantly non-ionic nature. Molecular weights of some of these compounds, where solubility permitted in nitrobenzene suggest that the compounds of composition $TiCl_3(OC_{10}H_7) \cdot 2L$ and $TiCl_2(OC_{10}H_7)_2 \cdot 2L$ are monomers whereas those of the composition $Ti(OC_{10}H_7)_4 \cdot L$ are dimers.

Significant ir bands (ν_{max}) of these adducts are due to $N-H$, $C=O$, $C-N$ and $N-C=O$ in case of amides and $P=O$, $P-N$ and $P-C$ in case of phosphoryl ligands (Table 1). The $\nu_{C=O}$ of the free amides occurring at 1685, 1670, 1680 and 1670 cm^{-1} for NMF, NMA, DMF and DMA gets lowered by $\sim 40-50 cm^{-1}$ on complexation suggesting coordination through the oxygen atom of the carbonyl group which is further supported by a trend in shifts of ν_{NH} , ν_{C-N} and $\nu_{N-C=O}$ vibrational modes towards higher regions⁷⁻⁹. In the case of dimethylsulphoxide adducts, the band present at 1050 cm^{-1} ($S=O$) in the pure ligand is lowered by $\sim 70-80 cm^{-1}$, while the band at 690 cm^{-1} ($C-S$) shifts to higher regions which supports oxygen coordination and is in agreement with the earlier reports¹⁰. Similarly, $\nu_{P=O}$ of triphenylphosphine oxide^{11,12} and hexamethylphosphoramide¹³ observed at 1192 and 1210 cm^{-1} , respectively is lowered by $\sim 50-60 cm^{-1}$ on adduct formation due to polarisation of the oxo-bond by the acceptor atom¹⁴. Other characteristic vibrations of hexamethylphosphoramide and triphenylphosphine oxide which are perturbed are due to ν_{P-N} and ν_{P-C} stretching modes. The two bands at 984 and 740

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL (cm^{-1}) DATA OF THE ADDUCTS OF NAPHTHOXIDES OF TITANIUM(IV) WITH AMIDES AND PHOSPHORYL LIGANDS

Compound	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis% Found/(Calcd.)		Molar conductance in PhNO_2 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$	Mol. Wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	ν_{max} (cm^{-1})				
			Ti	Cl			C=O or P=O	C N or P-N	N-C=O or P-C	Ti-O	Ti-Cl
A.2NMF	Brown	109	11.43 (11.55)	25.50 (25.63)	2.1	—	1638	1400 3290 ^c	765	608	352,348
A.2DMF	Dark brown	67	10.74 (10.82)	23.89 (24.01)	2.6	401 (443.5)	1635	1470	678	605	348,341
A.2NMA	Brown	85	10.79 (10.82)	23.90 (24.01)	3.0	—	1628	1300 3280 ^c	767	596	349,340
A.2DMA	Brown	105	10.00 (10.18)	22.41 (22.59)	4.1	410 (453.5)	1628	1524	735	595	341,338
A.2DMSO	Brown	91	10.47 (10.58)	23.36 (23.48)	3.3	489 (528)	960 ^a	730 ^b	—	599	351,346
B.2NMF	Light brown	88	9.02 (9.18)	13.51 (13.58)	2.0	—	1645	1419 3352 ^c	760	598	349
B.2DMF	Brown	64	8.58 (8.71)	12.73 (12.89)	2.1	—	1642	1475	665	592	342
B.2NMA	Brown	90	8.63 (8.71)	12.80 (12.89)	3.1	514 (551)	1638	1324 3342 ^c	763	608	346
B.2DMA	Brown	55	8.17 (8.29)	12.09 (12.26)	1.9	549 (579)	1640	1528	740	602	348
B.2DMSO	Brown	71	8.40 (8.56)	12.57 (12.66)	2.6	527 (561)	975 ^a	720 ^b	—	602	305
C.NMF	Light brown	179	7.00 (7.07)	—	1.0	1319 (679)	1648	1416 3355 ^a	758	602 598 508	—
C.DMF	Light brown	183	6.83 (6.93)	—	1.3	—	1646	1465	680	600 595 518	—
C.NMA	Brown	170	6.79 (6.93)	—	1.6	—	1640	1318 3345 ^c	758	601 592 510	—
C.DMA	Light brown	202	6.71 (6.79)	—	1.0	—	1642	1529	730	608 601 508	—
C.DMSO	Brown	196	6.77 (6.88)	—	1.1	—	900 ^a	730 ^b	—	602 598 512	—
A.2HMPA	Brownish red	110	7.27 (7.32)	16.07 (16.25)	4.1	605 (655)	1148	1056 994 750	—	602	351,348
A.2Ph ₃ PO	Red	72	5.57 (5.62)	12.33 (12.48)	3.4	—	1135	—	465 451	598	348,350
B.2HMPA	Brown	93	6.21 (6.29)	9.17 (9.31)	2.7	—	1158	1062 997 755	—	608	346
B.2Ph ₃ PO	Dull red	107	4.90 (4.99)	7.21 (7.39)	3.0	932 (961)	1145	—	474 458	604	350
C.HMPA	Light brown	179	5.79 (6.01)	—	1.0	1557 (799)	1164	1060 996 758	—	610 507	—
C.Ph ₃ PO	Light red	94	5.21 (5.35)	—	1.7	—	1148	—	476 460	606 505	—

A= $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2$, B= $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2$, C= $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_4$.
^a = $\nu(\text{S}=\text{O})$, ^b = $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$, ^c = $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$.

cm^{-1} (P-N) in parent HMPA shift to higher regions in its adducts possibly due to the increase in delocalisation of nitrogen electron pair towards the phosphorus atom¹⁴. The bands at 455 and 441 cm^{-1} (P-C) in case of pure Ph₃PO also move towards higher frequencies by $\sim 10\text{-}15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which agrees well with the earlier reports on such adducts. All these bands are given in Table 1.

Other important absorptions observed in the ir spectra are due to titanium-oxygen and titanium-chlorine stretching modes. The bands at 508-512

cm^{-1} due to bridging $\text{Ti} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \end{array} \text{Ti}$ modes in the parent

naphthoxides⁶ are absent in the compounds $\text{TiCl}_2 \cdot (\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot 2\text{L}$ and $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2 \cdot 2\text{L}$ suggesting the rupturing of naphthoxy-bridges on complexation with the ligands. These observations are in agreement with the earlier reports on the alkoxide and phenoxide adducts with various bases^{15,16}. Sharp bands in the region 590-610 cm^{-1} may be assigned to terminal $\nu_{\text{Ti}-\text{O}}$ stretching modes^{6,9}. The appearance of bands in the region 340-350 cm^{-1} (Ti-Cl) of the adducts suggest an octahedral environment around titanium^{9,17}. However, the adducts of titanium tetranaphthoxide naphtholate of composition $\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_4 \cdot \text{L}$ exhibit bands due to both

terminal Ti—O as well as bridging $\text{Ti} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \text{---} \end{array} \text{Ti}$ modes which suggest that in these compounds the bridging is retained even on adduct formation.

Thermogravimetric analysis of some of the adducts has been studied to determine their stability and mode of decomposition. From the weight changes noted in the thermograms of different compounds, it is inferred that the first step of decomposition involves the loss of base molecule at 170–220° followed by a similar trend of decomposition as observed for the parent naphthoxides⁶.

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